

CENIEH code Litho.NaiborSoitNdogo.0023**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Naibor Soit Ndogo**Locality** Naibor Ndogo**Municipality****Province** Olduvai Gorge**Country** Tanzania**Latitude** -2.974611**Longitude** 35.360778**MASL** 1479**Ref. Map****Map provider****Outcrop type** Massive outcrop**Original observations:**

Se encuentra en formato tabular en este afloramiento geológico precámbrico (Naibor Soit) y forma parte de la formación Kisele de Cuarcita - Tabular format quartzite in a Precambrian Outcrop (Naibor Soit). It is part of the Kisele quartzite formation

General description:

This is a polycrystalline quartz. It is also visible the presence of black minerals. Maybe, they are muskovites

Cortical surfaces**Morphology** Tabular Pebble**Touch** Coarse grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features****Imp. cracks****Joints**

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

It has rounded crystals of biotites. There are marks of a shear zone

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints Unidirectional**Touch****Bright****Microcracks****Bedding****Foliation****Texture****Packing****Grain detection**

Quartz grain features **A** & **B**

Type**Grain size****Sorting****Matrix type****% matrix****Cement type****% cement**

Other minerals Manganese oxides
 Iron oxides
 Back and heavy non-identified
 Pyrites

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Very poorly sorted
Orientation	Foliation
Grain type- 1	Straigh quartz grain limits
Grain size	Pebble (> 2 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Very angular
% Grains	100

Grain type 2

Grain size	
Sphericity	
Roundness	
% Grains	

Grain type 3

Grain size	
Elongation	
Roundness	
% Grains	

Type

Cement	
% cement	
Matrix	
% matrix	

Other minerals Rutile**Other minerals** Zircon**Other minerals** Muscovite**Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH.024

Quartz

Thin section Si NoXRF Si No

Creation 01/06/2023 11:54:32

Modification 17/04/2024 11:31:16

CENIEH code Litho.NaiborSoitNdogo.0024**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Naibor Soit Ndogo**Locality** Naibor Ndogo**Municipality****Province** Olduvai Gorge**Country** Tanzania**Latitude** -2.974611**Longitude** 35.360778**MASL** 1479**Ref. Map****Map provider****Outcrop type****Original observations:**

Se encuentra en formato tabular en este afloramiento geológico precámbrico (Naibor Soit) y forma parte de la formación Kisele de Cuarcita - Tabular format quartzite in a Precambrian Outcrop (Naibor Soit). It is part of the Kisele quartzite formation

General description:

This is a polycrystalline quartz.

Cortical surfaces

- Morphology
- Touch
- Inclusions
- Features
- Imp. cracks
- Joints

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

It has rounded crystals of biotites. There are marks of "cizaya"

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

- Joints Unidirectional
- Touch
- Bright
- Microcracks
- Bedding
- Foliation
- Texture
- Packing
- Grain detection

Quartz grain features A & B

- Type
- Grain size
- Sorting
- Matrix type
- % matrix
- Cement type
- % cement
- Other minerals
 - Manganese oxides
 - Iron oxides
 - Back and heavy non-identified
 - Pyrites

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Heterogeneous

Joints None

Texture

Packing

Sorting TS Very poorly sorted

Orientation

Grain type- 1 Straigh quartz grain limits

Grain size Pebble (> 2 mm)

Sphericity Very elongated

Roundness Very angular

% Grains 100

Grain type 2

Grain size

Sphericity

Roundness

% Grains

Grain type 3

Grain size

Elongation

Roundness

% Grains

Type

Cement

% cement

Matrix

% matrix

Other minerals Zircon

Other minerals Muscovite

Other minerals

Other minerals

Other minerals

Other minerals

CENIEH code Litho.PeñaMiel.0026**Collectors** Joseba Rios Garaizar**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Peña Miel**Locality** Nieva de Cameros**Municipality** Nieva de Cameros**Province** La Rioja**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.626281**Longitude** 42.230907**MASL** 781**Ref. Map** 241 (21-11)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Aflora junto al rio Iregua. Litología general: calizas, dolomías y margas, conglomerados y areniscas. Litología específica: calizas, margas, calizas nodulosas y radiolaritas, rocas volcánicas.- It crops out near the Iregua river. General lithology: limestones, dolomites, and marls.

General description:

Quartzite with high metamorphic degree: Polygonal grains recrystallised quartzite (PQ)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Soapy
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	Tridirectional

- | | | |
|---|--|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|--|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	Tridirectional
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Medium
Microcracks	High
Bedding	None
Foliation	Foliated
Texture	Soapy
Packing	Saturated
Grain detection	Impossible < 5 grains recognised with no boundaries

Quartz grain features

A

&

B with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

Type	AQ
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted

Matrix type

% matrix

Cement type

% cement

Other minerals

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Zoned
Joints	None
Texture	Porfidoblastic
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Well Sorted
Orientation	Bidirectional foliation
Grain type- 1	Abnormal coarse quartz grain
Grain size	Pebble (> 2 mm)
Sphericity	Very elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	70
Grain type 2	Quartz with 120° triple points
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Spherical
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	30
Grain type 3	
Grain size	
Elongation	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Type	AQ
Cement	
% cement	
Matrix	
% matrix	
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	Muscovite
Other minerals	Pyrite
Other minerals	
Other minerals	
Other minerals	

Colour is zoned. It can have two zones, one with big crystals and the other without it.

They are the same in the the thin section

CENIEH code Litho.Hornos.0031**Collectors** Joseba Rios Garaizar**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Hornos de la Peña**Locality** Tarriba**Municipality** San Felices de Buelna**Province** Cantabria**Country** Spain**Latitude** -4.029774**Longitude** 43.26132**MASL** 230**Ref. Map** 58 (18-05)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Procede del material de revuelto de las excavaciones antiguas. Litología genérica: calizas, dolomías y margas, conglomerados y areniscas. Litología específica; conglomerados, areniscas, arenas y margas. - It came from a mixed layer from the old excavation. Generic lithology: Limestones, marls, dolomites, conglomerates and sandstones

General description:

Quartzite: Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology

Touch

Inclusions

Features

Imp. cracks

Joints

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None
Touch Coarse grained
Bright None
Microcracks None
Bedding Clear
Foliation Unfoliated
Texture Saccharoid
Packing Floating
Grain detection Very easy >25 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features A
 &
 with ruffled and irregular limits
 B generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type MA
Grain size Coarse (>0.25)
Sorting Moderately sorted
Matrix type Grainy and siliceous
% matrix 5-20%
Cement type Ferruginous
% cement 5-20%

Other minerals Iron oxides
 Manganese oxides
 White mica
 Back and heavy non-identified
 Felspars

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Punctual or isolated
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	80
Grain type 2	Quartz with weathered borders
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	80
Grain type 3	Polycrystalline quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	20
Type	MA
Cement	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	5-20%
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	
Other minerals	
Other minerals	

CENIEH code Litho.Aranbaltza.0032**Collectors** Joseba Rios Garaizar**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Aranbaltza**Locality** Aranbaltza**Municipality** Barrika**Province** Bizkaia**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.96647**Longitude** 43.399137**MASL** 60**Ref. Map** 37 (21-04)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Procede del revuelto del yacimiento arqueológico de Aranbaltza, este tipo de material aflora en el lecho del ríachuelo junto al yacimiento. LITOLOGIA: 02 - Rocas detríticas de grano grueso (Areniscas). Dominante. DESCRIP: 116 - Areniscas y conglomerados. Geomorfología: Plataforma fluvial con escalonamientos naturales que coinciden con niveles arenosos de terrazas - It came from a mixed layer at Aranbaltza. This material crops out in a near riverbed area. Lithology: Sandstones

General description:

Quartzite: Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology** Tabular Pebble**Touch****Inclusions****Features****Imp. cracks****Joints**

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None**Touch** Coarse grained**Bright** None**Microcracks** None**Bedding** Clear**Foliation** Unfoliated**Texture** Saccharoid**Packing** Floating**Grain detection** Difficult 5-15 grains recognised
with plain and angular limits

Quartz grain features

A &
with ruffled and irregular limits

B generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type MA**Grain size** Medium (0.062 – 0.25)**Sorting** Very poorly sorted**Matrix type** Fluid and ferruginous**% matrix** 5-20%**Cement type****% cement****Other minerals** Iron oxides
Manganese oxides
White mica

Back and heavy non-identified

Felspars

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Floating
Sorting TS	Well Sorted
Orientation	Sedimentary stratification
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	99
Grain type 2	Polycrystalline quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	1
Grain type 3	Quartz with weathered borders
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	90
Type	MA
Cement	Carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	>20%
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Pyrite
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Feldspars
Other minerals	Rutile

CENIEH.035

Quartz

Thin section Si NoXRF Si No

Creation 01/06/2023 14:10:10

Modification 17/04/2024 11:31:45

CENIEH code Litho.Olduvai.0035**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olduvai**Locality** Naibor Ndogo**Municipality****Province** Olduvai Gorge**Country** Tanzania**Latitude** 35.359639**Longitude** -2.969278**MASL** 1484**Ref. Map****Map provider****Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:****General description:**

Very tiny fragment of quartz

Cortical surfaces

- Morphology
- Touch
- Inclusions
- Features
- Imp. cracks
- Joints

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

- Joints** None
- Touch** Fine
- Bright** High
- Microcracks** Low
- Bedding** None
- Foliation** Unfoliated
- Texture** Fine and grainy
- Packing** Saturated
- Grain detection** Impossible < 5 grains recognised with plain and angular limits

- Quartz grain features
 - A
 - B

- Type**
- Grain size** Coarse (>0.25)
- Sorting** Very poorly sorted
- Matrix type**
- % matrix**
- Cement type**
- % cement**
- Other minerals** Pyrites
Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Heterogeneous
Joints None
Texture Grain supported
Packing Saturated
Sorting TS Very poorly sorted
Orientation

Grain type- 1 Straigh quartz grain limits
Grain size Very coarse sand (1 - 2 mm)
Sphericity Very elongated
Roundness Very angular
% Grains 100

Grain type 2
Grain size
Sphericity
Roundness
% Grains

Grain type 3
Grain size
Elongation
Roundness
% Grains

Type
Cement
% cement
Matrix
% matrix

Other minerals Zircon
Other minerals
Other minerals
Other minerals
Other minerals
Other minerals

colourless. Polycrystalline quartz

CENIEH code Litho.TercerNaibor.0037**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Tercer Naibor, Olduvai**Locality** Naibor Ndogo**Municipality****Province** Olduvai Gorge**Country** Tanzania**Latitude** 35.359639**Longitude** -2.969278**MASL** 1484**Ref. Map****Map provider****Outcrop type** Massive outcrop**Original observations:**

Forma parte de la formación Kisele de Cuarcita. - It is part of the Kisele quartzite formation

General description:

In binoculars, there are green and acicular minerals (Sillimallite) together with red to brown minerals in form of Tourmaline, probably. Thin section is quite complex, and it is near to be a granulite rather than a quartzite.

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch** Coarse grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** None**Imp. cracks** Absence**Joints** None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None**Touch** Coarse grained**Bright** Low**Microcracks** Low**Bedding** None**Foliation** Foliated**Texture** Granular**Packing** Tangential**Grain detection** Difficult 5-15 grains recognised
with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features A
&
with appearance of regrowth
B

Type CA**Grain size** Coarse (>0.25)**Sorting** Very poorly sorted**Matrix type** Grainy and siliceous**% matrix** 5-20%**Cement type****% cement**

Other minerals Iron oxides
Manganese oxides
White mica
Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Zoned
Joints	None
Texture	Nematoblastic
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Very poorly sorted
Orientation	Foliation
Grain type- 1	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity	Very elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	40
Grain type 2	Bohm lamellae
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity	Very elongated
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	40
Grain type 3	Recrystallised quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	20
Type	
Cement	Nonexistent
% cement	
Matrix	Siliceous
% matrix	<5%
Other minerals	Kyanite
Other minerals	Feldspars
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals
Other minerals	Estaurolita

CENIEH code Litho.TercerNaibor.0038**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Tercer Naibor, Olduvai**Locality** Naibor Ndogo**Municipality****Province** Olduvai Gorge**Country** Tanzania**Latitude** 35.359639**Longitude** -2.969278**MASL** 1484**Ref. Map****Map provider****Outcrop type** Massive outcrop**Original observations:**

Forma parte de la formación Kisele de Cuarcita - Part of the Kiselle formation of quartzite

General description:

Possibly tourmalines detected through binoculars. In thin section non-quartz minerals are abundant and in addition to there are muskovites. This is a polycrystalline quartz.

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** None**Imp. cracks** Absence**Joints** None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints Unidirectional**Touch** Coarse grained**Bright** Medium**Microcracks** None**Bedding** None**Foliation** Unfoliated**Texture** Granular**Packing** Tangential**Grain detection** Difficult 5-15 grains recognised
with plain and angular limits

A
Quartz grain features &
 B

Type**Grain size** Coarse (>0.25)**Sorting** Very poorly sorted**Matrix type** Grainy and siliceous**% matrix** <5%**Cement type****% cement**

Other minerals Manganese oxides
 White mica
 Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Zoned
Joints None
Texture
Packing Complete
Sorting TS Very poorly sorted
Orientation

Grain type- 1 Abnormal coarse quartz grain
Grain size Very coarse sand (1 - 2 mm)
Sphericity Elongated
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 60

Grain type 2 Straigh quartz grain limits
Grain size Very coarse sand (1 - 2 mm)
Sphericity Elongated
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 40

Grain type 3
Grain size
Elongation
Roundness
% Grains

Type

Cement
% cement
Matrix
% matrix

Other minerals Zircon**Other minerals** Rutile**Other minerals** Biotite**Other minerals** Muscovite**Other minerals** Tourmaline**Other minerals** Sillimalite

Possibly tourmalines detected through binoculars. In thin section non-quartz minerals are abundant and in addition to there are muskovites. This is a polycrystalline quartz.

CENIEH code Litho.Miño.0039**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Ambrona**Locality** Ambrona**Municipality** Miño de Medinaceli**Province** Soria**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.512028**Longitude** 41.168994**MASL** 1131**Ref. Map** 435 (23-17)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Litología genérica: calizas, dolomías y margas, conglomerados y areniscas. Litología específica: dolomías, calizas y calizas nodulosas.- Generic lithology: Limestones, dolomite, marl, conglomerates and sandstones

General description:

Quartzite: Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	Bidirectional

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|--|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|--|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	Bidirectional
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features A & B with appearance of regrowth

Type	MA
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Argillitic
% matrix	<5%
Cement type	
% cement	

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	Manganese oxides
	White mica
	Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	Unidirectional
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Tangential
Sorting TS	Well Sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Well rounded
% Grains	80
Grain type 2	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Well rounded
% Grains	20
Grain type 3	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	5
Type	MA
Cement	
% cement	
Matrix	
% matrix	
Other minerals	Feldspars
Other minerals	Goethite
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals
Other minerals	Pyrite
Other minerals	Glauconite

CENIEH code Litho.Tormes.0091**Collectors** Joseba Rios Garaizar**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Alba de Tormes**Locality** Alba de Tormes**Municipality** Alba de Tormes**Province** Salamanca**Country** Spain**Latitude** -5.524750**Longitude** 40.812589**MASL** 806**Ref. Map** 479 (14-19)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Litología genérica: cuarcitas, pizarras, areniscas, calizas y vulcanitas. Litología específica: pizarras, grauwacas o arcosas, conglomerados y calizas. - Generic lithology: Quartzites, shales, sandstones, limestones and volcanic rocks.

General description:

It is colourless. It can be quartzite or quartz. I think it is more quartzite because it has a clear porphyroblastic structure. Quartz grains are generally serrated, but some other not. Abnormal coarsening grain recrystallised quartzite (AQ)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** None**Imp. cracks****Joints**

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints Tridirectional**Touch** Fine**Bright** High**Microcracks** Low**Bedding** None**Foliation** Folliated**Texture** Fine and grainy**Packing** Saturated**Grain detection** Impossible < 5 grains recognised
with plain and angular limits

Quartz grain features

A

&

B

with no boundaries

Type AQ**Grain size** Coarse (>0.25)**Sorting** Very poorly sorted**Matrix type****% matrix****Cement type****% cement****Other minerals** Pyrites
Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Porfidoblastic
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	Foliation

Grain type- 1	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity	Very elongated
Roundness	Very angular
% Grains	95

Grain type 2	Abnormal coarse quartz grain
Grain size	Pebble (> 2 mm)
Sphericity	Very elongated
Roundness	Very angular
% Grains	10

Grain type 3	Bohm lamellae
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Very angular
% Grains	5

Type AQ

Cement
% cement
Matrix
% matrix

Other minerals Zircon
Other minerals Muscovite
Other minerals
Other minerals
Other minerals
Other minerals

It is colourless. It can be quartzite or quartz. I think it is more quartzite because it has a clear porfidoblastic structure. Quartz grains are generally serrated, but some other not.

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanpe.0092**Collectors** Joseba Rios Garaizar**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Peña de Arlanpe**Locality** Lemoa**Municipality** Lemoa**Province** Bizkaia**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.931083**Longitude** 43.430012**MASL** 204**Ref. Map** 62 (22-05)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Massive outcrop**Original observations:**

Filones de origen hidrotermal que son relativamente abundantes en el sinclinorio vasco, en sus variedades lechosa y cristalina. Existen de filones poco extensos en las inmediaciones (<500 m) de la cueva de Arlanpe. - Hydrothermal quartz abundace at the Basque Syncline. There are few around the Arlanpe cave

General description:

Colourless quartz

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** None**Imp. cracks****Joints**

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints Tridirectional**Touch** Fine**Bright** High**Microcracks** Low**Bedding** None**Foliation** Foliated**Texture** Fine and grainy**Packing** Saturated**Grain detection** Impossible < 5 grains recognised
with plain and angular limits

Quartz grain features

A

&

B

Type**Grain size** Coarse (>0.25)**Sorting** Very poorly sorted**Matrix type****% matrix****Cement type****% cement****Other minerals** Pyrites
Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity** Very homogeneous**Joints** Tridirectional**Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1** Straigh quartz grain limits**Grain size** Pebble (> 2 mm)**Sphericity** Very elongated**Roundness** Very angular**% Grains** 100**Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals** Muscovite**Other minerals** Pyrite**Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0152**Collectors** Joseba Rios Garaizar**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzon**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.698139**Longitude** 42.340404**MASL** 853**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Posición secundaria, cauce de un río. From a riverbed, secondary position quartzite

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Fine grained
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	Unidirectional

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and angular limits

A

Quartz grain features

&

with ruffled and irregular limits

B

generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	5-20%

Other minerals	Manganese oxides
	White mica
	Back and heavy non-identified
	Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Floating
Sorting TS	Very poorly sorted
Orientation	

Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	70

Grain type 2	Quartz with weathered borders
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	20

Grain type 3	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation	Spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	10

Type	MA
Cement	Fluid and ferruginous
% cement	>20%
Matrix	Unknown
% matrix	

Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Goethite
Other minerals	Feldspars
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Garnet

CENIEH code Litho.Utrillas.0175**Collectors** Ana Álvarez Fernández**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Utrillas**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.460552**Longitude** 42.319416**MASL** 975**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Cuarcitas de las facies Utrillas - Quartzite from the Utrillas facies

General description:

It is difficult to assess this quartzite because the thin section is almost destroyed. There are several breaks in the quartz grains border and their inner parts, also.

Preliminary, it is assigned to the Bulging recrystallised quartzite (BQ)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch****Inclusions****Features****Imp. cracks****Joints**

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints

None

Touch

Fine grained

Bright

Medium

Microcracks

Low

Bedding

Non-clear

Foliation

Foliated

Texture

Fine and grainy

Packing

Saturated

Grain detection Easy 15-25 grains recognised
with appearance of regrowth

A**Quartz grain features**

&
with no boundaries

B**Type**

BQ

Grain size

Medium (0.062 – 0.25)

Sorting

Well sorted

Matrix type

Nonexistent

% matrix**Cement type**

Nonexistent

% cement**Other minerals**

White mica
Back and heavy non-identified

Iron oxides

White mica

Pyrites

20X INNER

50X INNER

250X INNER

250X INNER

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Very poorly sorted
Orientation	

Grain type- 1	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	85

Grain type 2	Recrystallised quartz grains
Grain size	Medium silt (0.016 - 0.031 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	15

Grain type 3	Undulate extinction quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	85

Type	BQ
Cement	Carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	
% matrix	

Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals
Other minerals	
Other minerals	

It is difficult to assess this quartzite because the thin section is almost destroyed. There are several breaks in the quartz grains border and their inner parts, also.

CENIEH code Litho.Utrillas. 0176**Collectors** Ana Álvarez Fernández**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Utrillas**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.460552**Longitude** 42.319416**MASL** 975**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Cuarcitas de las facies Utrillas - Quartzite from the Utrillas facies

General description:

Bulging recrystallised quartzite (BQ). We originally classified through binocular this piece as RQ because of the high bright and extremely vitreous and bright lustre. It is clear in this and another samples from the Utrilla formation that lustre and bright were slightly modified by the cements of the sedimentary strata the nodules are inserted.

Cortical surfaces

Morphology

Touch

Inclusions

Features

Imp. cracks

Joints

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

- Joints** Unidirectional
Touch Fine
Bright High
Microcracks Low
Bedding None
Foliation Foliated
Texture Fine
Packing Saturated
Grain detection Difficult 5-15 grains recognised
with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

- Quartz grain features**
A
&
with no boundaries
B

- Type** BQ
Grain size Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting Well sorted
Matrix type Nonexistent
% matrix
Cement type
% cement

- Other minerals** Iron oxides
Back and heavy non-identified
White mica
Pyrites
Back and heavy non-identified
White mica

20X INNER

50X INNER

250X INNER

250X INNER

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Heterogeneous
Joints Unidirectional
Texture Grain supported
Packing Saturated
Sorting TS Very poorly sorted
Orientation

Grain type- 1 Saturated quartz grains
Grain size Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity Tendent to spherical
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 70

Grain type 2 Recrystallised quartz grains
Grain size Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity Spherical
Roundness Rounded
% Grains 30

Grain type 3 Bohm lamellae
Grain size Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation Tendent to spherical
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 5

Type BQ
Cement Argillitic
% cement >20%
Matrix
% matrix

Other minerals Rutile
Other minerals Clay minerals
Other minerals Unidentified opaque minerals
Other minerals Mica flake
Other minerals

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0177**Collectors** Ana Álvarez Fernández**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.460552**Longitude** 42.319416**MASL** 975**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

It was possible to detect some glauconites and zircons through the binoculars. The coexistence of rounded and angular quartz grain shapes it is also clear, as partial cements. In thin section, the cements are present but in very small percentages. It is a Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular Pebble
Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Río. Está bastante pulido y tiene golpeados fluviales y marcas de litófgos y líquenes

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

A**Quartz grain features**

&

with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement

B

Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Argillitic
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%

Other minerals	White mica
	Iron oxides
	Back and heavy non-identified
	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Tangential
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	90
Grain type 2	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	90
Grain type 3	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	10
Type	MA
Cement	Carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	5-20%
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Chlorite
Other minerals	Glauconite
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0178**Collectors** Ana Álvarez Fernández**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Burgos**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.460552**Longitude** 42.319416**MASL** 975**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA).

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular Pebble	
Touch	Fine	
Inclusions	Iron oxides	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Absence	
Joints	Unidirectional	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

cortex fluvial

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

A**Quartz grain features**

&

with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement

B

Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Argillitic
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%

Other minerals	White mica
	Iron oxides
	Back and heavy non-identified
	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Heterogeneous
Joints Unidirectional
Texture Grain supported
Packing Tangential
Sorting TS Moderately sorted
Orientation

Grain type- 1 Detritic quartz grains
Grain size Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity Tendent to spherical
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 90

Grain type 2 Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity Tendent to spherical
Roundness Subrounded
% Grains 90

Grain type 3 Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Elongation Tendent to spherical
Roundness Subrounded
% Grains 10

Type MA
Cement Carbonated
% cement <5%
Matrix Argillitic
% matrix 5-20%

Other minerals Feldspars
Other minerals Clay minerals
Other minerals Rutile
Other minerals Glauconite
Other minerals Chlorite
Other minerals Micas

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0179**Collectors** Ana Álvarez Fernández**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.460552**Longitude** 42.319416**MASL** 975**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA). The quantity of non-quartz minerals is really high

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** None**Imp. cracks** Absence**Joints** None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

cortex de ladera

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None**Touch** Coarse grained**Bright** None**Microcracks** None**Bedding** Non-clear**Foliation** Unfoliated**Texture** Saccharoid**Packing** Punctual or isolated**Grain detection** Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits**A****Quartz grain features**

&

with ruffled and irregular limits

B

generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type MA**Grain size** Fine (<0.062)**Sorting** Moderately sorted**Matrix type** Grainy and siliceous**% matrix** 5-20%**Cement type** Argillitic**% cement** 5-20%

Other minerals Iron oxides
Manganese oxides
Back and heavy non-identified
Manganese oxides
Back and heavy non-identified
White mica

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Floating
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	Sedimentary stratification
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Medium silt (0.016 - 0.031 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	100
Grain type 2	
Grain size	
Sphericity	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Grain type 3	
Grain size	
Elongation	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Type	MA
Cement	Argillitic
% cement	5-20%
Matrix	Carbonated
% matrix	5-20%
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Pyrite
Other minerals	Glauconite
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0180**Collectors** Ana Álvarez Fernández**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.460552**Longitude** 42.319416**MASL** 975**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA). Very similar to previous one

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** None**Imp. cracks** Absence**Joints** None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

cortex de ladera

20X CORT

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None**Touch** Coarse grained**Bright** None**Microcracks** None**Bedding** Non-clear**Foliation** Unfoliated**Texture** Saccharoid**Packing** Punctual or isolated**Grain detection** Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits**A****Quartz grain features**

&

with ruffled and irregular limits

B

generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type MA**Grain size** Fine (<0.062)**Sorting** Moderately sorted**Matrix type** Grainy and siliceous**% matrix** 5-20%**Cement type** Argillitic**% cement** 5-20%

Other minerals Iron oxides
Manganese oxides
Back and heavy non-identified
Manganese oxides
Back and heavy non-identified
White mica

20X INNER

50X INNER

250X INNER

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	Unidirectional
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Floating
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	Sedimentary stratification
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	100
Grain type 2	
Grain size	
Sphericity	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Grain type 3	
Grain size	
Elongation	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Type	MA
Cement	Argillitic
% cement	5-20%
Matrix	Carbonated
% matrix	5-20%
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Chlorite
Other minerals	Glauconite
Other minerals	Feldespato
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0181**Collectors** Ana Álvarez Fernández**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.460552**Longitude** 42.319416**MASL** 975**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA). The quantity of non-quartz minerals is really high

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** None**Imp. cracks** Absence**Joints** None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

cortex de ladera

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None**Touch** Coarse grained**Bright** None**Microcracks** None**Bedding** Non-clear**Foliation** Unfoliated**Texture** Saccharoid**Packing** Punctual or isolated**Grain detection** Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits**A****Quartz grain features**

&

with ruffled and irregular limits

B

generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type MA**Grain size** Fine (<0.062)**Sorting** Moderately sorted**Matrix type** Grainy and siliceous**% matrix** 5-20%**Cement type** Argillitic**% cement** 5-20%

Other minerals Iron oxides
Manganese oxides
Back and heavy non-identified
Manganese oxides
Back and heavy non-identified
White mica

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Floating
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	Sedimentary stratification
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Medium silt (0.016 - 0.031 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	100
Grain type 2	
Grain size	
Sphericity	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Grain type 3	
Grain size	
Elongation	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Type	MA
Cement	Argillitic
% cement	5-20%
Matrix	Carbonated
% matrix	5-20%
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Pyrite
Other minerals	Glauconite
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0182**Collectors** Ana Álvarez Fernández**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.460552**Longitude** 42.319416**MASL** 975**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

This thin section is interesting as it is the first one I have seen this type. It is a transition from the Polygonal grains recrystallised quartzite (PQ) to the Abnormal coarsening grain recrystallised quartzite (AQ). It is possible to see some areas of each of the zone, also zones in which polygonised grains were put together at specific orientations and separated at others, in a similar shape of a chessboard texture.

Cortical surfaces

Morphology

Touch

Inclusions

Features

Imp. cracks

Joints

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints

None

Touch

Soapy

Bright

High

Microcracks

Low

Bedding

None

Foliation

Unfoliated

Texture

Fine

Packing

Saturated

Grain detection Difficult 5-15 grains recognised
with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

A

Quartz grain features

&

with no boundaries

B

Type

AQ

Grain size

Fine (<0.062)

Sorting

Well sorted

Matrix type

Nonexistent

% matrix

Cement type

Nonexistent

% cement

Other minerals

White mica
Pyrites

Pyrites

White mica

20X INNER

50X INNER

250X INNER

250X INNER

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Zoned
Joints	None
Texture	Foam
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	Foliation
Grain type- 1	Quartz with 120° triple points
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	
Grain type 2	Abnormal coarse quartz grain
Grain size	Pebble (> 2 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Very angular
% Grains	
Grain type 3	Undulate extinction quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	100
Type	AQ
Cement	
% cement	
Matrix	
% matrix	
Other minerals	Muscovite
Other minerals	

This thin section is interesting as it is the first one I have seen this type. It is a transition from the Polygonal grains to the abnormal grain coarsing

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0183**Collectors** Ana Álvarez Fernández**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.460552**Longitude** 42.319416**MASL** 975**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

It is impossible to classify this rock as quartzite using the methodology used. This rock section has alternations, one part is a breccia (metamorphic or volcanic) and another quartz in bands. In between, it is possible to see the CA quartzite

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble	
Touch	Fine grained	
Inclusions	Iron oxides	
Features	Vacuole	
Imp. cracks	Fluvial	
Joints	None	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features	A
	&
	with plain and angular limits
	B

Type	CA
Grain size	Coarse (>0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Nonexistent
% matrix	
Cement type	Nonexistent
% cement	
Other minerals	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Pyrites
	White mica
	Pyrites
	Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Zoned
Joints	None
Texture	Nematoblastic
Packing	
Sorting TS	Very poorly sorted
Orientation	Foliation
Grain type- 1	Undulate extinction quartz grains
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	40
Grain type 2	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	40
Grain type 3	Straigh quartz grain limits
Grain size	Pebble (> 2 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	20
Type	CA
Cement	Carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	<5%
Other minerals	

It is impossible to classify this rock as quartzite using the methodology used. This rock section has alternation, one part is a breccia (metamorphic or volcanic) and quartz in bands.

CENIEH code Litho.CuestaBajada.0196**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Cuesta de la Bajada**Locality** Cuesta de la Bajada**Municipality** Teruel**Province** Teruel**Country** Spain**Latitude** -1.121103**Longitude** 40.356161**MASL** 866**Ref. Map** 567 (27-22)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Terraza, Cuarzitas muy escasas y pequeñas, predominio de calizas. - Fluvial terrace, scant quartzites and very small. Major materials are the limestones

General description:

This is a polycrystalline quartz

Cortical surfaces

- Morphology
- Touch
- Inclusions
- Features
- Imp. cracks
- Joints

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

- Joints
- Touch
- Bright
- Microcracks
- Bedding
- Foliation
- Texture
- Packing
- Grain detection

Quartz grain features A & B

- Type
- Grain size
- Sorting
- Matrix type
- % matrix
- Cement type
- % cement
- Other minerals

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Heterogeneous

Joints None

Texture

Packing

Sorting TS

Orientation

Grain type- 1 Straigh quartz grain limits

Grain size Pebble (> 2 mm)

Sphericity Very elongated

Roundness Very angular

% Grains 100

Grain type 2

Grain size

Sphericity

Roundness

% Grains

Grain type 3

Grain size

Elongation

Roundness

% Grains

Type

Cement

% cement

Matrix

% matrix

Other minerals Zircon

Other minerals Muscovite

Other minerals Garnet

Other minerals

Other minerals

Other minerals

CENIEH code Litho.CuestaBajada.0197**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Cuesta de la Bajada**Locality** Cuesta de la Bajada**Municipality** Teruel**Province** Teruel**Country** Spain**Latitude** -1.121103**Longitude** 40.356161**MASL** 866**Ref. Map** 567 (27-22)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Cuarcita predominante, en tamaños pequeños (menos de 5 cm, las mayores poco más de 10 cm). También caliza y quizás sílex - Quartzite predominates, in small sizes (less than 5 cm, the biggest ones are just over 10 cm). There are also limestones and, maybe, flint

General description:

It is in transition towards the BQ. It is important to see some regrowths on thin section too. The latter makes us to maintain it into the orthoquartzite world, Therefore, it is classified as Sutured grain orthoquartzite (SO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular Pebble
Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	None

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Foliated
Texture	Fine and grainy
Packing	Saturated
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

A

Quartz grain features

&

with appearance of regrowth

B

Type	SO
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Moderately sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	<5%
Cement type	
% cement	

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Pyrites
	Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	Foliation
Grain type- 1	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	95
Grain type 2	Undulate extinction quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	95
Grain type 3	Recrystallised quartz grains
Grain size	Medium silt (0.016 - 0.031 mm)
Elongation	Spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	5
Type	SO
Cement	Nonexistent
% cement	
Matrix	
% matrix	
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	
Other minerals	
Other minerals	

It is in transition towards the BQ. It is important to see some regrowths on thin section too. The latter makes us to maintain it into the orthoquartzite world

CENIEH code Litho.CuestaBajada.0198**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Cuesta de la Bajada**Locality** Cuesta de la Bajada**Municipality** Teruel**Province** Teruel**Country** Spain**Latitude** -1.121103**Longitude** 40.356161**MASL** 866**Ref. Map** 567 (27-22)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Cuarcita predominante, en tamaños pequeños (menos de 5 cm, las mayores poco más de 10 cm). También caliza y quizás sílex - Quartzite predominates, in small sizes (less than 5 cm, the biggest ones are just over 10 cm). There are also limestones and, maybe, flint

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Carbonates**Features** None**Imp. cracks** Absence**Joints** None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

and iron oxides

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None**Touch** Fine grained**Bright** Low**Microcracks** Low**Bedding** None**Foliation** Unfoliated**Texture** Compact and grainy**Packing** Complete**Grain detection** Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits**A****Quartz grain features**

&

with appearance of regrowth

B**Type** OO**Grain size** Medium (0.062 – 0.25)**Sorting** Well sorted**Matrix type** Grainy and siliceous**% matrix** <5%**Cement type****% cement**

Other minerals Iron oxides
 White mica
 Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Complete
Sorting TS	Well Sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	80
Grain type 2	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	40
Grain type 3	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	20
Type	OO
Cement	
% cement	
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	<5%
Other minerals	Glaucanite
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	
Other minerals	
Other minerals	

CENIEH code Litho.CuestaBajada.0199**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Cuesta de la Bajada**Locality** Cuesta de la Bajada**Municipality** Teruel**Province** Teruel**Country** Spain**Latitude** -1.121103**Longitude** 40.356161**MASL** 866**Ref. Map** 567 (27-22)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Terraza - Fluvial terrace

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA). It is relatively non consolidated

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble	
Touch	Fine grained	
Inclusions	Carbonates	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Absence	
Joints	None	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

and iron oxides

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A &
	B with plain and rounded limits
Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	Más del 20%
Cement type	
% cement	
Other minerals	White mica Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	Unidirectional
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Punctual or isolated
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	Sedimentary stratification
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	90
Grain type 2	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	5
Grain type 3	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	5
Type	MA
Cement	Ferruginous
% cement	5-20%
Matrix	Fluid and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Glaucanite
Other minerals	Chlorite
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Tourmaline

CENIEH code Litho.CuestaBajada.0200**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Cuesta de la Bajada**Locality** Cuesta de la Bajada**Municipality** Teruel**Province** Teruel**Country** Spain**Latitude** -1.121103**Longitude** 40.356161**MASL** 866**Ref. Map** 567 (27-22)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Terraza - Fluvial terrace

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular Pebble
Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	None

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

and carbonates

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|--|--|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	Medium
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with appearance of regrowth

Quartz grain features

A

&

B

with plain and angular limits

Type	OO
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Moderately sorted
Matrix type	
% matrix	
Cement type	Siliceous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	White mica Iron oxides Pyrites

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	Unidirectional
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	Foliation
Grain type- 1	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	90
Grain type 2	Undulate extinction quartz grains
Grain size	
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	90
Grain type 3	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	10
Type	OO
Cement	Fluid and carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	
% matrix	
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Garnet
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	
Other minerals	

CENIEH code Litho.CuestaBajada.0201**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Cuesta de la Bajada**Locality** Cuesta de la Bajada**Municipality** Teruel**Province** Teruel**Country** Spain**Latitude** -1.121103**Longitude** 40.356161**MASL** 866**Ref. Map** 567 (27-22)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Secundario - Secondary deposit

General description:

This is a limestone

Cortical surfaces

- Morphology
- Touch
- Inclusions
- Features
- Imp. cracks
- Joints

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

- Joints
- Touch
- Bright
- Microcracks
- Bedding
- Foliation
- Texture
- Packing
- Grain detection

Quartz grain features | A & B

- Type
- Grain size
- Sorting
- Matrix type
- % matrix
- Cement type
- % cement
- Other minerals

Thin section characterisation

- Homogeneity
- Joints
- Texture
- Packing
- Sorting TS
- Orientation

- Grain type- 1
- Grain size
- Sphericity
- Roundness
- % Grains

- Grain type 2
- Grain size
- Sphericity
- Roundness
- % Grains

- Grain type 3
- Grain size
- Elongation
- Roundness
- % Grains

- Type
- Cement
- % cement
- Matrix
- % matrix

- Other minerals

Limestone

CENIEH code Litho.CuestaBajada.0202**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Cuesta de la Bajada**Locality** Cuesta de la Bajada**Municipality** Teruel**Province** Teruel**Country** Spain**Latitude** -1.121103**Longitude** 40.356161**MASL** 866**Ref. Map** 567 (27-22)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Secundario - Secondary deposit

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	Non-clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A
	& with plain and angular limits
B	
Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Moderately sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides White mica Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Tangential
Sorting TS	Well Sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	80
Grain type 2	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	10
Grain type 3	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	10
Type	MA
Cement	Fluid and carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	5-20%
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals
Other minerals	

CENIEH code Ambrona**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Litho.Miño.0216**Locality** Ambrona**Municipality** Miño de Medinaceli**Province** Soria**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.498131**Longitude** 41.160519**MASL** 1142**Ref. Map** 435 (23-17)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Yacimiento de Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria - Archaeological site of Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli

General description:

Subgrain rotation recrystallised quartzite (RQ) in transition to Grain boundary migration recrystallised quartzite (MQ), as can be seen by thin section

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	None

- | | | |
|---|--|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Fine
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Fine
Packing	Saturated
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with no boundaries

Quartz grain features A & B
with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type	RQ
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted

Matrix type
% matrix
Cement type
% cement

Other minerals White mica
Back and heavy non-identified
Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Foam
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	Foliation

Grain type- 1	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Very angular
% Grains	40

Grain type 2	Recrystallised quartz grains
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	60

Grain type 3	Bohm lamellae
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	5

Type	RQ
Cement	Nonexistent
% cement	
Matrix	Nonexistent
% matrix	

Other minerals	Chlorite
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Muscovite
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	

RQ in transition to MQ

CENIEH code Litho.Miño.0217**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Ambrona**Locality** Ambrona**Municipality** Miño de Medinaceli**Province** Soria**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.498131**Longitude** 41.160519**MASL** 1142**Ref. Map** 435 (23-17)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Yacimiento de Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria. Archaeological site of Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria, Spain

General description:

It was complicated to understand the thin section due to the high saturation quartz grains it has. The presence of different grains, allow us to classify it in the sedimentary world.

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble	
Touch	Fine grained	
Inclusions	Iron oxides	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Absence	
Joints	None	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A &
	B with plain and rounded limits
Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Moderately sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides White mica Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Very angular
% Grains	60
Grain type 2	Undulate extinction quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	40
Grain type 3	
Grain size	
Elongation	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Type	CA
Cement	Carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	<5%
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	
Other minerals	
Other minerals	

It was complicated to understand the thin section due to the high saturation quartz grains it has

CENIEH code Litho.Miño.0218**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Ambrona**Locality** Ambrona**Municipality** Miño de Medinaceli**Province** Soria**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.498131**Longitude** 41.160519**MASL** 1142**Ref. Map** 435 (23-17)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Yacimiento de Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria - Archaeological site of Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology****Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** None**Imp. cracks** Absence**Joints** None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None**Touch** Coarse grained**Bright** None**Microcracks** None**Bedding** Clear**Foliation** Unfoliated**Texture** Saccharoid**Packing** Floating

Grain detection Difficult 5-15 grains recognised
with ruffled and irregular limits
generated by the effect of matrix or
cement

Quartz grain features A
&
B
with plain and rounded limits

Type MA**Grain size** Fine (<0.062)**Sorting** Moderately sorted**Matrix type** Grainy and siliceous**% matrix** 5-20%**Cement type** Ferruginous**% cement** 5-20%

Other minerals Iron oxides
Manganese oxides
White mica
Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Tangential
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	Sedimentary stratification
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	90
Grain type 2	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	10
Grain type 3	
Grain size	
Elongation	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Type	MA
Cement	Fluid and carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	5-20%
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals
Other minerals	Biotite

CENIEH code Litho.Miño.0219**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Ambrona**Locality** Ambrona**Municipality** Miño de Medinaceli**Province** Soria**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.498131**Longitude** 41.160519**MASL** 1142**Ref. Map** 435 (23-17)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Yacimiento de Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria - Archaeological site of Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli

General description:

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	None

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|--|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfolded
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A &
	B with plain and angular limits
Type	MA
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Moderately sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides White mica Pyrites

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Heterogeneous
Joints
Texture Grain supported
Packing Complete
Sorting TS Moderately sorted
Orientation

Grain type- 1 Detritic quartz grains
Grain size Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity Tendent to spherical
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 80

Grain type 2 Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity Elongated
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 16

Grain type 3 Quartz with weathered borders
Grain size Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation Spherical
Roundness Rounded
% Grains 4

Type CA
Cement Unknown
% cement
Matrix Argillitic
% matrix <5%

Other minerals Zircon
Other minerals Mica flake
Other minerals Micas
Other minerals Clay minerals
Other minerals Glauconite
Other minerals Chlorite

CENIEH code Litho.Miño.0220**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Ambrona**Locality** Ambrona**Municipality** Miño de Medinaceli**Province** Soria**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.498131**Longitude** 41.160519**MASL** 1142**Ref. Map** 435 (23-17)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Yacimiento de Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria. Archaeological site of Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria, Spain

General description:

Sutured grain orthoquartzite (SO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular Pebble
Touch	Fine grained
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Gravitational
Joints	None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

also manganese oxides

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

Quartz grain features
 A
 &
 with appearance of regrowth
 B

Type	SO
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	
% matrix	
Cement type	
% cement	

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	Pyrites
	Back and heavy non-identified
	White mica

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	95
Grain type 2	Recrystallised quartz grains
Grain size	Medium silt (0.016 - 0.031 mm)
Sphericity	Spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	5
Grain type 3	Undulate extinction quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	95
Type	SO
Cement	Argillitic
% cement	<5%
Matrix	
% matrix	
Other minerals	Biotite
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Pyrite
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	

CENIEH code Litho.Miño.0221**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Ambrona**Locality** Ambrona**Municipality** Miño de Medinaceli**Province** Soria**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.498131**Longitude** 41.160519**MASL** 1142**Ref. Map** 435 (23-17)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Yacimiento de Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria - Archaeological site of Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli

General description:

Badly done thin section. It is very dirty. Probably it is a OO, but the quantity of Syntaxial opvergrowths is small due to the quality of the thin section

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	None

- | | | |
|---|--|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	None
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features	A
	&
	with appearance of regrowth
	B

Type	OO
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Well sorted

Matrix type	
% matrix	
Cement type	
% cement	

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	Black and heavy non-identified
	White mica
	Felspars

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	40
Grain type 2	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity	Spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	60
Grain type 3	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	40
Type	CA
Cement	Argillitic
% cement	<5%
Matrix	
% matrix	
Other minerals	Glauconite
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Tourmaline
Other minerals	

Badly done thin section. It is very dirty. Probably it is a OO, but the quantity of Syntaxial opvergrowths is small due to the quality of the thin section

CENIEH code Litho.Miño.0222**Collectors** Patricia Bello Alonso**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Ambrona**Locality** Ambrona**Municipality** Miño de Medinaceli**Province** Soria**Country** Spain**Latitude** -2.498131**Longitude** 41.160519**MASL** 1142**Ref. Map** 435 (23-17)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Indetermined**Original observations:**

Yacimiento de Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria. Archaeological site of Ambrona, Miño de Medinaceli, Soria, Spain

General description:

Quartz

Cortical surfaces

Morphology

Touch

Inclusions

Features

Imp. cracks

Joints

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
- Grey Green Yellow
- Black Orange Red

Joints

Touch

Bright

Microcracks

Bedding

Foliation

Texture

Packing

Grain detection

Quartz grain features

A

&

B

Type

Grain size

Sorting

Matrix type

% matrix

Cement type

% cement

Other minerals

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Heterogeneous
Joints None
Texture Nematoblastic
Packing Saturated
Sorting TS Poorly sorted
Orientation

Grain type- 1 Straigh quartz grain limits
Grain size Very coarse sand (1 - 2 mm)
Sphericity Very elongated
Roundness Very angular
% Grains 50

Grain type 2 Saturated quartz grains
Grain size Very coarse sand (1 - 2 mm)
Sphericity Elongated
Roundness Very angular
% Grains 50

Grain type 3
Grain size
Elongation
Roundness
% Grains

Type

Cement
% cement
Matrix
% matrix

Other minerals Micas
Other minerals Tourmaline
Other minerals Mica flake
Other minerals Zircon
Other minerals

CENIEH code Litho.Olmos de Atapuerca.0228**Collectors** Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Thin section and binocular characterisation are different. Undoubtedly, thin section petrography is the most relevant one, therefore, therefore, it is classified as: Subgrain rotation recrystallised quartzite (RQ). It is important to mention that when going into high resolution, grains are less visible and the texture seems to be more vitreous.

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Soapy
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	None

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Córtex secundario, muy pulido, posiblemente de tipo eólico

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	Unidirectional
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	Medium
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	Non-clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Tangential

Grain detection

with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features	A	&
	B	

Type	CA
Grain size	Coarse (>0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	<5%
Cement type	Argillitic
% cement	<5%

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	Pyrites
	Back and heavy non-identified
	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Pyrites

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Porfidoblastic
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	Bidirectional foliation
Grain type- 1	Polycrystalline quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	85
Grain type 2	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	15
Grain type 3	Bohm lamellae
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Angular
% Grains	5
Type	RQ
Cement	
% cement	
Matrix	
% matrix	
Other minerals	Turmalina
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble	
Touch	Fine grained	
Inclusions	Iron oxides	
Features	Vacuole	
Imp. cracks	Fluvial	
Joints	None	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

fluvial

Inner surfaces

<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	Clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Impossible < 5 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

A

Quartz grain features

&

with ruffled and irregular limits

B

generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type	MA
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	>20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	5-20%

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	Manganese oxides
	Back and heavy non-identified
	Iron oxides
	Pyrites
	Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology** Tabular Pebble**Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** Vacuole**Imp. cracks** Absence**Joints**

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Iuvial

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None**Touch** Coarse grained**Bright** None**Microcracks** None**Bedding** Non-clear**Foliation** Unfoliated**Texture** Saccharoid**Packing** Floating

Grain detection Difficult 5-15 grains recognised
with ruffled and irregular limits
generated by the effect of matrix or
cement

Quartz grain features A
&
B
with plain and rounded limits

Type MA**Grain size** Medium (0.062 – 0.25)**Sorting** Moderately sorted**Matrix type** Siliceous**% matrix** 5-20%**Cement type** Argillitic**% cement** 5-20%

Other minerals Iron oxides
White mica
Back and heavy non-identified
Iron oxides
Manganese oxides
Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology** Tabular Pebble**Touch** Fine grained**Inclusions** Iron oxides**Features** Vacuole**Imp. cracks** Absence**Joints**

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

fluvial

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None**Touch** Coarse grained**Bright** None**Microcracks** None**Bedding** Non-clear**Foliation** Unfoliated**Texture** Saccharoid**Packing** Floating

Grain detection Difficult 5-15 grains recognised
with ruffled and irregular limits
generated by the effect of matrix or
cement

Quartz grain features A
&
B
with plain and rounded limits

Type MA**Grain size** Coarse (>0.25)**Sorting** Very poorly sorted**Matrix type** Grainy and siliceous**% matrix** >20%**Cement type** Argillitic**% cement** 5-20%

Other minerals Iron oxides
White mica
Back and heavy non-identified
Iron oxides
Manganese oxides
Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

Wacka

CENIEH code Litho.PinedadelaSierra.0261**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Pineda de la Sierra**Locality** Pineda de la Sierra**Municipality** Pineda de la Sierra**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.32642**Longitude** 42.305887**MASL** 1118**Ref. Map** 239 (20-11)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Massive outcrop**Original observations:**

Talud en la carretera BU-820 - Obtained in a road talus at the BU-820

General description:

This rock seems to be a hornfel. Originally, it is a quartz arenite with very fine grains. They seems to be folded and some other minerals detected put this stone into the first stages of metamorphism (due to pression)

Petroolith: Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular clast	
Touch	Coarse grained	
Inclusions	Iron oxides	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Absence	
Joints	Tridirectional	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Fine and grainy
Packing	Saturated
Grain detection	Impossible < 5 grains recognised with no boundaries

Quartz grain features	A	&
	B	

Type	MA
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Argillitic
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	
% cement	
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides Pyrites Back and heavy non-identified Manganese oxides Pyrites

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Punctual or isolated
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	Foliation
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Medium silt (0.016 - 0.031 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	100
Grain type 2	
Grain size	
Sphericity	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Grain type 3	
Grain size	
Elongation	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Type	MA
Cement	Argillitic
% cement	>20%
Matrix	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	Sillimalite
Other minerals	Chloritoid
Other minerals	Muscovite

CENIEH code Litho.PinedadelaSierra.0259**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Pineda de la Sierra**Locality** Pineda de la Sierra**Municipality** Pineda de la Sierra**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.32642**Longitude** 42.305887**MASL** 1118**Ref. Map** 239 (20-11)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Massive outcrop**Original observations:**

Talud en la carretera BU-820 - Obtained in a road talus at the BU-820

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular clast
Touch	Coarse grained
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	Bidirectional

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|---------------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	Bidirectional
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	Non-clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

A

Quartz grain features

&

B

with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type	MA
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Argillitic
% matrix	>20%
Cement type	
% cement	

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Felspars
	Iron oxides
	Manganese oxides
	Pyrites

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Matrix supported
Packing	Punctual or isolated
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	Sedimentary stratification
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	100
Grain type 2	
Grain size	
Sphericity	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Grain type 3	
Grain size	
Elongation	
Roundness	
% Grains	
Type	MA
Cement	Nonexistent
% cement	
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	>20%
Other minerals	Feldspars
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals
Other minerals	Chloritoid

CENIEH code Litho.OlmosdeAtapuerca.0253**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Soapy
Inclusions	Carbonates
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	None

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	Non-clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

A

Quartz grain features

&

with ruffled and irregular limits

B

generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type	CA
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Argillitic
% cement	<5%

Other minerals	White mica
	Iron oxides
	Felspars
	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Heterogeneous
Joints	Unidirectional
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Complete
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	60
Grain type 2	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	30
Grain type 3	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	10
Type	CA
Cement	Carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	<5%
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Glauconite
Other minerals	Chlorite
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Unidentified opaque minerals

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble	
Touch	Soapy	
Inclusions	Carbonates	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Fluvial	
Joints	None	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	Non-clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features	A
	&
	with ruffled and irregular limits
B	generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type	CA
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Argillitic
% cement	<5%

Other minerals	White mica
	Iron oxides
	Felspars
	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Subgrain rotation recrystallised quartzite (RQ)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble	
Touch	Soapy	
Inclusions	Carbonates	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Absence	
Joints	Bidirectional	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

También tiene óxidos, sobretodo en las zonas de diaclasa

Inner surfaces

<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	Bidirectional
Touch	Fine
Bright	Medium
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Foliated
Texture	Fine
Packing	Saturated
Grain detection	Impossible < 5 grains recognised with no boundaries

Quartz grain features	A
	& with ruffled, irregular and thin limits
	B

Type	RQ
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Nonexistent
% matrix	
Cement type	Nonexistent
% cement	
Other minerals	Iron oxides White mica Back and heavy non-identified White mica Pyrites Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology
Touch
Inclusions
Features
Imp. cracks
Joints

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints Unidirectional
Touch Fine grained
Bright Low
Microcracks Medium
Bedding None
Foliation Unfoliated
Texture Compact and grainy
Packing Complete
Grain detection Easy 15-25 grains recognised
with appearance of regrowth

Quartz grain features
A &
with plain and rounded limits
B

Type OO
Grain size Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting Moderately sorted
Matrix type Argillitic
% matrix <5%
Cement type
% cement
Other minerals Iron oxides
Calcites
Back and heavy non-identified
Pyrites
Iron oxides
Manganese oxides

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code Litho.OlmosdeAtapuerca.0245**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Bulging recrystallised quartzite (BQ)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble		
Touch	Soapy		
Inclusions	Iron oxides		
Features	None		
Imp. cracks	Absence		
Joints	None		
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow	
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red	

Inner surfaces

<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Foliated
Texture	Fine and grainy
Packing	Saturated
Grain detection	Impossible < 5 grains recognised with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

Quartz grain features	A	
	B	& with no boundaries

Type	BQ
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Nonexistent
% matrix	
Cement type	
% cement	

Other minerals	White mica
	Iron oxides
	Manganese oxides
	Pyrites
	Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Homogeneous
Joints None
Texture Foam
Packing Saturated
Sorting TS Moderately sorted
Orientation Foliation

Grain type- 1 Saturated quartz grains
Grain size Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Sphericity Elongated
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 70

Grain type 2 Recrystallised quartz grains
Grain size Medium silt (0.016 - 0.031 mm)
Sphericity Spherical
Roundness Well rounded
% Grains 20

Grain type 3 Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size Fine sand (0.125 - 0.25 mm)
Elongation Elongated
Roundness Rounded
% Grains 10

Type BQ

Cement
% cement
Matrix
% matrix

Other minerals Pyrite
Other minerals Mica flake
Other minerals Zircon
Other minerals Chlorite
Other minerals Rutile
Other minerals

como CENIEH.F.004

CENIEH code Litho.OlmosdeAtapuerca.0246**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical pebble	
Touch	Soapy	
Inclusions	Carbonates	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Absence	
Joints	None	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Foliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with appearance of regrowth

Quartz grain features	A
	&
	with plain and rounded limits
	B

Type	OO
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Moderately sorted
Matrix type	Nonexistent
% matrix	
Cement type	Argillitic
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides White mica Back and heavy non-identified White mica Back and heavy non-identified Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Complete
Sorting TS	Well Sorted
Orientation	Foliation
Grain type- 1	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	40
Grain type 2	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	40
Grain type 3	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	20
Type	OO
Cement	Carbonated
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Nonexistent
% matrix	
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Chlorite
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Glauconite
Other minerals	Rutile

Thin section unveils the higher presence (than the one expected on binoculars) of saturated quartz grain limits

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical pebble	
Touch	Soapy	
Inclusions	Carbonates	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Absence	
Joints	None	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Foliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with appearance of regrowth

Quartz grain features	A
	&
	with plain and rounded limits
	B

Type	OO
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Moderately sorted
Matrix type	Nonexistent
% matrix	
Cement type	Argillitic
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides White mica Back and heavy non-identified White mica Back and heavy non-identified Iron oxides

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Sutured grain orthoquartzite (SO)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch Soapy
Inclusions Iron oxides

Features

Imp. cracks Absence

Joints None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None
Touch Fine grained
Bright Medium
Microcracks Low
Bedding None
Foliation Unfoliated
Texture Fine and grainy
Packing Saturated
Grain detection Impossible < 5 grains recognised
with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

Quartz grain features
A
&
with no boundaries
B

Type SO
Grain size Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting Well sorted
Matrix type Argillitic
% matrix
Cement type Ferruginous
% cement <5%
Other minerals Iron oxides
White mica
Black and heavy non-identified
White mica
Manganese oxides
Pyrites

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical pebble
Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Gravitational
Joints	None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Sólo es jabonoso, o es más jabonoso en las zonas fotografiadas en las que se ve bien cómo es el lustre de las fases utrillas y que es más parecida a lo que vi

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with appearance of regrowth

Quartz grain features
A
 &
 with plain and rounded limits
B

Type	OO
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	
% matrix	
Cement type	Argillitic
% cement	<5%

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Back and heavy non-identified
	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Calcites

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular pebble
Touch	Fine grained
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	Clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

A

Quartz grain features

&

B

with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement

Type	MA
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Argillitic
% cement	>20%

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	Back and heavy non-identified
	Manganese oxides
	Iron oxides
	Back and heavy non-identified
	Felspars

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0252**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Fine grained
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Gravitational
Joints	None

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|--|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

It also has some vegetal signs

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|---------------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Punctual or isolated
Grain detection	Very easy >25 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A
	B
Type	MA
Grain size	Coarse (>0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides
	Manganese oxides
	Black and heavy non-identified
	White mica

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Tangential
Sorting TS	Poorly sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	59
Grain type 2	Quartz with weathered borders
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	40
Grain type 3	Polycrystalline quartz grains
Grain size	Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	1
Type	MA
Cement	Carbonated
% cement	5-20%
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	<5%
Other minerals	Garnet
Other minerals	Micas
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	Biotite
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0260**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular Pebble	
Touch	Fine	
Inclusions	Manganese oxides	
Features	Vegetal	
Imp. cracks	Fluvial	
Joints	None	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Also Iron oxides

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	Medium
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Very easy >25 grains recognised with plain and angular limits

Quartz grain features	A
	&
	with plain and rounded limits
	B

Type	CA
Grain size	Coarse (>0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	<5%
Cement type	Siliceous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides White mica Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity Heterogeneous
Joints None
Texture Grain supported
Packing Tangential
Sorting TS Very poorly sorted
Orientation Sedimentary stratification

Grain type- 1 Detritic quartz grains
Grain size Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity Elongated
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 45

Grain type 2 Detritic quartz grains
Grain size Medium sand (0.25 - 0.5 mm)
Sphericity Tendent to spherical
Roundness Subrounded
% Grains 45

Grain type 3 Polycrystalline quartz grains
Grain size Coarse sand (1 mm)
Elongation Elongated
Roundness Subangular
% Grains 10

Type CA

Cement
% cement

Matrix Argillitic
% matrix <5%

Other minerals Rutile

Other minerals Muscovite

Other minerals Pyrite

Other minerals Glauconite

Other minerals

Other minerals

The quantity of non-quartz minerals is quite limited

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Pineda de la Sierra**Locality** Pineda de la Sierra**Municipality** Pineda de la Sierra**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.32642**Longitude** 42.305887**MASL** 1118**Ref. Map** 239 (20-11)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Massive outcrop**Original observations:**

Talud en la carretera BU-820 - Obtained in a road talus at the BU-820

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular clast
Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	None
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised

Quartz grain features	A	with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
	B	with plain and angular limits

Type	MA
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Argillitic
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vegetal
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	Unidirectional

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|--|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised

Quartz grain features	A	with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
	B	with plain and rounded limits

Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Fluid and ferruginous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides White mica Black and heavy non-identified Pyrites

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

2 mode distribution

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vegetal
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	Unidirectional

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|--|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A & B with plain and rounded limits
Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Siliceous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides White mica Black and heavy non-identified Pyrites Felspars

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

Two mode distribution

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vegetal
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	Unidirectional

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|--|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A &
	B with plain and rounded limits
Type	CA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	<5%
Cement type	Siliceous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Black and heavy non-identified
	Pyrites
Felspars	

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Tabular clast	
Touch	Fine	
Inclusions	Iron oxides	
Features	Vegetal	
Imp. cracks	Absence	
Joints	None	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	Clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A
	B

Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Argillitic
% cement	5-20%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides White mica Back and heavy non-identified Pyrites Felspars

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

Two modes distribution

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Flatten Pebble	
Touch	Fine	
Inclusions	Iron oxides	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Fluvial	
Joints	None	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	Medium
Microcracks	None
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Very easy >25 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A
	B
	&
	with plain and rounded limits

Type	MA
Grain size	Coarse (>0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Siliceous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides Back and heavy non-identified White mica

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

Grey and purple

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Matrix or cemented quartz arenite (MA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Coarse grained
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	None

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|---------------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	None
Bedding	Non-clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A
	& with plain and angular limits
	B

Type	MA
Grain size	Coarse (>0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	5-20%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides White mica Black and heavy non-identified Pyrites Felspars

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code Litho.Arlanzon.0243**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch Fine

Inclusions Iron oxides

Features None

Imp. cracks Gravitational

Joints None

White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None

Touch Coarse grained

Bright None

Microcracks Medium

Bedding Non-clear

Foliation Unfoliated

Texture Granular

Packing Punctual or isolated

Grain detection Difficult 5-15 grains recognised

Quartz grain features

A with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement

&

B with plain and angular limits

Type CA

Grain size Medium (0.062 – 0.25)

Sorting Well sorted

Matrix type Grainy and siliceous

% matrix <5%

Cement type Argillitic

% cement <5%

Other minerals Iron oxides
Manganese oxides
White mica
Black and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Zoned
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Tangential
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	Sedimentary stratification
Grain type- 1	Detritic quartz grains
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Elongated
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	65
Grain type 2	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	30
Grain type 3	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	5
Type	CA
Cement	
% cement	
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	<5%
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	Feldspars
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Micas

This one has no links between thin section and binocular characteriation

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Flatten Pebble	
Touch	Fine	
Inclusions	Iron oxides	
Features	Vacuole	
Imp. cracks	Fluvial	
Joints	None	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	Non-clear
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Saccharoid
Packing	Floating
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A
	& with plain and angular limits
	B

Type	MA
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Moderately sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	5-20%
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	5-20%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides White mica Back and heavy non-identified Pyrites

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Arlanzón**Locality** Arlanzón**Municipality** Arlanzón**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.469457**Longitude** 42.32232**MASL** 974**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Ribera del río Arlanzón a su paso por la localidad de Arlanzón (Burgos) - Streambed of Arlanzón River at the locality of Arlanzón, Burgos

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	None

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

- White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with appearance of regrowth

Quartz grain features
 A
 &
 with no boundaries
 B

Type	OO
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	
% matrix	
Cement type	
% cement	

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code Litho.OlmosdeAtapuerca.0248**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO). Discrepancies between the exact petrogenetic type using the binoculars and the thin section may be caused due to the presence of silica and iron oxides cements

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Soapy
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	None

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|--|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

extremely soapy

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|---------------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	Bidirectional
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Medium
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Fine and grainy
Packing	Saturated
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

A

Quartz grain features

&

with no boundaries

B

Type	SO
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Unknown
% matrix	
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	Manganese oxides
	White mica
	Back and heavy non-identified
	Pyrites

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Homogeneous
Joints	Bidirectional
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Saturated
Sorting TS	Moderately sorted
Orientation	Foliation
Grain type- 1	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	60
Grain type 2	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	30
Grain type 3	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Coarse silt (0.031 - 0.062 mm)
Elongation	Elongated
Roundness	Subangular
% Grains	10
Type	OO
Cement	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Argillitic
% matrix	<5%
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Mica flake
Other minerals	Glauconite
Other minerals	Biotite
Other minerals	Feldspars

Thin section does not clearly show the saturated quartz grains, therefore, we cannot mach both non-destructive and thin section characterisation

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	None

- | | | |
|--|--|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features

A

&

B

with appearance of regrowth

Type	OO
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Unknown
% matrix	
Cement type	Siliceous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides White mica Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Sutured grain orthoquartzite (SO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble
Touch	Soapy
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	None

- | | | |
|--|--|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	Medium
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Foliated
Texture	Fine and grainy
Packing	Saturated
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

Quartz grain features

A

&

with no boundaries

B

Type	SO
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	
% matrix	
Cement type	
% cement	

Other minerals	Iron oxides
	White mica
	Pyrites
	Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

It could be even being BQ

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch	Fine
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vegetal
Imp. cracks	Absence
Joints	None

- | | | |
|--|---------------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Tangential
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features	A	&
	B	

Type	CA
Grain size	Coarse (>0.25)
Sorting	Very poorly sorted
Matrix type	Unknown
% matrix	
Cement type	Siliceous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	White mica Iron oxides Back and heavy non-identified Pyrites

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch	Soapy
Inclusions	Iron oxides
Features	Vacuole
Imp. cracks	Fluvial
Joints	None

- | | | |
|--|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Inner surfaces

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> White | <input type="checkbox"/> Blue | <input type="checkbox"/> Brown |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey | <input type="checkbox"/> Green | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Black | <input type="checkbox"/> Orange | <input type="checkbox"/> Red |

Joints	None
Touch	Fine grained
Bright	None
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with appearance of regrowth

Quartz grain features

A

&

B

with ruffled, irregular and thin limits

Type	OO
Grain size	Fine (<0.062)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Unknown
% matrix	
Cement type	Ferruginous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Manganese oxides Pyrites

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces**Morphology**

Touch Fine
Inclusions Iron oxides
Features None
Imp. cracks Fluvial
Joints None

White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Inner surfaces

White Blue Brown
 Grey Green Yellow
 Black Orange Red

Joints None
Touch Fine grained
Bright Low
Microcracks Low
Bedding None
Foliation Unfoliated
Texture Compact and grainy
Packing Tangential
Grain detection Easy 15-25 grains recognised with plain and rounded limits

Quartz grain features
 A
 &
 with appearance of regrowth
 B

Type OO
Grain size Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting Well sorted
Matrix type
% matrix
Cement type
% cement

Other minerals Iron oxides
 White mica
 Back and heavy non-identified

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**

CENIEH code Litho.OlmosdeAtapuerca.0242**Collectors** Javier Llamazares y Felipe Cuartero**Analysed by** Alejandro Prieto**Place name** Olmos de Atapuerca**Locality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Municipality** Olmos de Atapuerca**Province** Burgos**Country** Spain**Latitude** -3.535105**Longitude** 42.390416**MASL** 957**Ref. Map** 200 (19-10)**Map provider** IGME**Outcrop type** Deposit**Original observations:**

Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Syntaxially overgrown orthoquartzite (OO)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble	
Touch	Soapy	
Inclusions	Siliceous	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Fluvial	
Joints	None	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Fine
Bright	Low
Microcracks	Medium
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Compact and grainy
Packing	Complete
Grain detection	Easy 15-25 grains recognised with appearance of regrowth

Quartz grain features	A
	B
	&
	with plain and rounded limits

Type	OO
Grain size	Medium (0.062 – 0.25)
Sorting	Well sorted
Matrix type	Unknown
% matrix	
Cement type	Siliceous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Black and heavy non-identified White mica Pyrites

Thin section characterisation

Homogeneity	Very homogeneous
Joints	None
Texture	Grain supported
Packing	Complete
Sorting TS	Well Sorted
Orientation	
Grain type- 1	Quartz grains with syntaxial
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Rounded
% Grains	50
Grain type 2	Concave-convex quartz grain limits
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Sphericity	Spherical
Roundness	Well rounded
% Grains	30
Grain type 3	Saturated quartz grains
Grain size	Very fine sand (0.062 - 0.125 mm)
Elongation	Tendent to spherical
Roundness	Subrounded
% Grains	20
Type	OO
Cement	Argillitic
% cement	<5%
Matrix	Nonexistent
% matrix	
Other minerals	Clay minerals
Other minerals	Rutile
Other minerals	Muscovite
Other minerals	Tourmaline
Other minerals	Zircon
Other minerals	

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Arenas, gravas y arcillas - Sands, gravels and clays

General description:

Clastic grained quartz arenite (CA)

Cortical surfaces

Morphology	Spherical Pebble	
Touch	Soapy	
Inclusions	Iron oxides	
Features	None	
Imp. cracks	Fluvial	
Joints	None	
<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Inner surfaces

<input type="checkbox"/> White	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Brown
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grey	<input type="checkbox"/> Green	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow
<input type="checkbox"/> Black	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Red

Joints	None
Touch	Coarse grained
Bright	Medium
Microcracks	Low
Bedding	None
Foliation	Unfoliated
Texture	Granular
Packing	Punctual or isolated
Grain detection	Difficult 5-15 grains recognised with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement
Quartz grain features	A
	&
	with plain and angular limits
	B

Type	CA
Grain size	Coarse (>0.25)
Sorting	Moderately sorted
Matrix type	Grainy and siliceous
% matrix	<5%
Cement type	Siliceous
% cement	<5%
Other minerals	Iron oxides Pyrites Back and heavy non-identified Felspars Calcites White mica

Thin section characterisation**Homogeneity****Joints****Texture****Packing****Sorting TS****Orientation****Grain type- 1****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 2****Grain size****Sphericity****Roundness****% Grains****Grain type 3****Grain size****Elongation****Roundness****% Grains****Type****Cement****% cement****Matrix****% matrix****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals****Other minerals**